

Bio-Combined Heat & power plant integrated with calcium looping: How environmentally friendly this integration is?

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ABSTRACT

A crucial step in achieving the Net-Zero Emissions Scenario goals is thought to be integrating CO₂ capture technologies into Bio-Combined Heat and Power (Bio-CHP) facilities. The present study investigates the environmental impact of a Bio-CHP plant integrated with Calcium Looping (CaL) CO₂ capture through Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology, comparing it with a state-of-the-art Mono-Ethanol-Amine (MEA) based CO₂ capture. The environmental performance of the two capture technologies is examined using a cradle-to-gate analysis based on the ReCiPe 2016 assessment method and considering three CO₂ transportation scenarios, i. e., onshore pipelines (T1), onshore and offshore pipelines (T2), and onshore pipelines, liquefaction and offshore shipping (T3). The findings of the LCA study show that the first transportation case (T1) generates the best environmental results. The CO₂ liquefaction and ship transportation (T3) raises the GWP impact by 313 kg CO₂ eq./t CO₂ captured and determines a 13-fold increase in Fossil fuel Depletion Potential (FDP) compared to T1. When comparing the two CO₂ capture technologies, the CaL system exhibits better environmental performance, with ten out of eleven impact indicators showing lower values. Beyond the environmental benefits, this research demonstrates that CaL technology surpasses the amine scrubbing system in net power output (e.g., 50.6 vs. 26.6 MW_e) and direct fossil emissions (e.g., -2748.2 vs. -1079.9 kg CO₂/t wood), despite a higher fuel consumption (e.g., 224.7 vs. 135.3 MW_{LHV}). These findings underscore the advantages of integrating post-combustion CO₂ capture with efficient CO₂ transportation strategies, paving the way for a cleaner and more sustainable heat and power sector.

1. Introduction

Human activity has been steadily changing the environment for thousands of years, yet these changes have been primarily local. Nevertheless, massive amounts of CO₂ and other greenhouse gases (GHGs) released into the atmosphere, as a result of utilizing fossil fuels, have surpassed all the advancements made throughout the Industrial Revolution (Wilberforce et al., 2021). Even though GHGs are essential for life on Earth due to how they contribute to maintaining an appropriate temperature (Yoro and Daramola, 2020), higher atmospheric concentrations trap more heat, which causes global warming and climate change (Li et al., 2023).

Carbon dioxide is the most significant anthropogenic GHG, with atmospheric concentration reaching a historic 419 parts per million (ppm)

in 2023, in contrast to 280 ppm registered in the 19th century. In addition, CO₂ emissions, which comprise around 73% of human-caused releases, will persist in the atmosphere for hundreds to thousands of years (Calvin et al., 2023). Accordingly, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) predicts that if significant global measures to reduce CO₂ emissions are not adopted, the global surface temperature will rise by 1.5 °C–4 °C during the next century. Climate change, hence global warming, will ultimately result in severe and permanent effects on both aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. These consequences will include thinning glaciers and ice sheets, rising sea levels, ocean acidification and deoxygenation, and severe weather events like hurricanes, droughts, and heat waves (Calvin et al., 2023).

According to the International Energy Agency (IEA) reports, power generation emissions reduced by 1.3% in 2019. However, these still

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represent the most significant contribution with a share of 41% of worldwide CO₂ emissions. Coal is the most commonly utilized energy source, responsible for 29% of these emissions, followed by natural gas (9%) and oil (2%). Furthermore, in addition to power generation, 23% of global CO₂ emissions are related to the industry sector and a similar amount to transport (IEA, 2020). Consequently, these three sectors must be decarbonized to avoid further CO₂ emission peaks using all available methods, e.g., improved process efficiency, renewable energy, fuel substitution, and carbon capture technologies. According to the IEA, in 2020, the power industry was rapidly moving toward carbon neutrality, with GHG emissions decreasing by around 3.3% primarily due to the improvements in the generation of green energy and the COVID-19 pandemic-induced drop in energy usage. Nevertheless, in 2021 the CO₂ emissions of the energy sector rebounded by over 900 Mt increase (nearly 7%), resulting in a total of 14.6 Gt (IEA, 2021), and, in 2022, by yet another 220 Mt, reaching a record-high of 14.8 Gt (IEA, 2023).

As reported by IEA, the industrial sector was responsible for about 37% of the total energy use in 2022. A primary cause of the growth in power consumption over the past ten years has been the steady production expansion in high-energy industrial sectors (e.g., iron and steel, cement, pulp and paper). Additionally, industries were responsible for an estimated 9.0 Gt of CO₂ emissions in 2022, about 25% of all GHG releases (IEA, 2023). Thus, the industrial sector needs to adopt several measures to curb GHG emissions and move toward the Net-Zero Emission (NZE) Scenario, including increased material and energy efficiency, a more rapid switch to renewable energy sources, and a quicker integration of Carbon Capture Utilization and Storage (CCUS) technologies into the production process (IEA, 2023), which is one of the most promising medium-term options for decreasing CO₂ emissions.

During the past ten years, amine gas sweetening has proved to be a viable method for post-combustion CO₂ capture, as two full-scale industrial facilities (Boundary Dam and Petra Nova) are currently in operation (Wu et al., 2014). Yet, there are several disadvantages such as high energy costs from solvent regeneration and rust-related equipment concerns (Tao and Brander, 2024).

Chemical-looping approaches use oxygen carriers or CO₂ sorbents as chemical intermediates to efficiently remove CO₂ while consuming the least amount of energy (Fennell, 2015). Oxygen carriers are generally solid metal oxides designed to carry out multiple oxidation and reduction cycles to provide the oxygen required for fuel burning without diluting the exhaust stream with nitrogen, as in air combustion, or using an Air Separation Unit (ASU). On the other hand, CO₂ sorbents go through a cycle of creating and breaking chemical bonds with CO₂ molecules, capturing them from a low-concentration environment (e.g., flue gas) and releasing them in a concentrated stream. Calcium Looping (CaL) is one of the latter techniques, in which the sorbent, calcium oxide (CaO), reacts with CO₂ to produce calcium carbonate (CaCO₃), which is then decomposed in a different reactor, generating a nearly pure stream of CO₂ (Abad, 2015). The chemical reactions involved in the process are:

According to scientific literature, a CCUS system might greatly enhance environmental performance and contribute to achieving climate objectives at currently operating combined heat and power (CHP) facilities (Kumar et al., 2023). Kumar et al. (2023) studied the performance of a Bio-CHP plant in a district heating system with different CO₂ capture units, characterized by different energy needs per unit of CO₂ captured from the flue gases. Another study carried out by Wang et al. (2023) looked at the range of potential CO₂ capture amounts, as well as the effect of CO₂ capture on waste-fired CHP plant performance. Dong et al. (2024) assessed the possibility of national emissions reductions with an approach centered around the dynamic modeling of two operating modes, allowing or not a reduction in energy production.

However, in addition to assessing only the reduction of CO₂ emissions, a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) study may be used to quantify the

overall environmental impact of various CO₂ mitigation technologies. Yang et al. (2024) performed an LCA on a mass-integrated CHP system that operates without CCS under ideal conditions, showing that the most ecological harm is attributed to the construction and operation of the system. Di Marcoberardino et al. (2018) investigated a natural gas-based micro-CHP system using a membrane reactor and without carbon capture from economic and environmental points of view. The outcome of the LCA analysis shows a small contribution to the environmental impact categories due to micro-CHP production, maintenance, and end-of-life, except for the human health indicator. An LCA study of the biomass-to-energy chain for a CHP plant using biomass gasification has been carried out by Costa et al. (2022) considering wood chips or a mixture of wood chips with olive waste to produce 20 kW and 40 kW of electric and thermal power, respectively, but without considering the possibility of achieving negative emission by CO₂ sequestration. The environmental assessment shows that the largest contributors to the total normalized environmental impact are gasification and combustion at 54.6% and ash management at 42.8%. Meanwhile, the wood chip supply and oil pomace supply chains account for 1.9% and 0.8%, respectively. Dias et al. (2023) studied the sustainability of a calcium-looping thermochemical energy storage plant using solar power and showed that the environmental performance may be increased by making use of total carbonator purge, while utilizing as well the water vapor as a fluidization agent at the calciner. However, in this case, the CaL system is not used to remove CO₂ from combustion products. Carbone et al. (2023) presented an LCA analysis of GHG emissions using post-combustion CaL in the steel industry, comparing two steel production routes, Blast Furnace with Basic Oxygen Furnace and Direct Reduction with Electric Arc Furnace (i.e., BF-BOF and DR-EAF). The DR-EAF process showed significantly lower GHG emissions (e.g., 0.9 t CO₂ eq./t of liquid steel produced) compared to the BF-BOF process (e.g., 2.1 t CO₂ eq./t of liquid steel produced).

The literature review shows a lack of analysis regarding LCA studies on CaL systems for the decarbonization of CHP plants. The available works mainly focus on the environmental impact of the decarbonization strategies, such as waste-heat recovery (Yang et al., 2024), improved energy efficiency (Di Marcoberardino et al., 2018), and fuel substitution (biomass) (Costa et al., 2022). On the other hand, the analyses featuring CaL systems investigate different applications, e.g., energy storage (Dias et al., 2023) or the decarbonization of industrial processes, e.g., steel plants (Carbone et al., 2023). Thus, in order to address the existing literature gap, the present research aims to evaluate the environmental performance of the CaL-based CO₂ capture system integrated within a Bio-CHP facility. The environmental performance of the CaL system is compared against the conventional amine-based (Mono-Ethanol-Amine (MEA)) CO₂ capture system to get a comprehensive understanding of the CaL technology's environmental impact and how it compares to the most developed carbon capture solution. This research presents significant key novel contributions that include a comprehensive environmental assessment of two carbon capture systems integrated with a Bio-CHP plant, alongside an analysis of three proposed CO₂ transportation routes within the Asturias region of Spain.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. General description of the investigated cases

The Bio-CHP plant used as a reference for the present study consists of a circulating fluidized bed (CFB)-based combustion boiler, firstly assigned to burn locally sourced coal. Then, it was later modified to operate with waste biomass co-combustion and is currently undergoing a retrofit to handle biomass input only (De Lena et al., 2024). Further information related to the Bio-CHP plant, including the process flow diagram, is given in the Supplementary material file. The Bio-CHP plant's flue gases comprise 69.38 %_{vol} N₂, 13.05 %_{vol} CO₂, 11.75 %_{vol} H₂O, 5.00 %_{vol} O₂, and 0.82 %_{vol} Ar. The integration of the

post-combustion MEA and CaL-based CO₂ capture systems within the Bio-CHP plant is illustrated in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively.

As shown in Fig. 1, the flue gas from the Bio-CHP plant is cooled in a direct contact cooler (DCC) and then fed into the bottom of the absorption column in a counter-current with the aqueous MEA absorption solution. Over the length of the column, the CO₂ is absorbed into the amine liquid solution, and at the top of the column, the decarbonized gas is further scrubbed with water to reduce amine-compound emissions to the atmosphere before being sent to the stack. The rich MEA solution is preheated, recovering heat from the lean solvent that exits the reboiler to reduce the regeneration duty and sent to the top of the stripper. The heat required for solvent regeneration is provided by steam extracted from the steam turbine of the Bio-CHP power plant as a bleeding stream. The regenerated solvent preheats the rich stream and is further cooled close to ambient temperature. Then, it is mixed with a make-up of fresh MEA solution before being recycled to the absorber. The gaseous phase, resulting at the top of the stripper, is cooled, and the generated liquid phase, containing mainly water and MEA, is fed back at the top of the stripper. The remaining stream, containing mainly CO₂, is intercooled and compressed to the transportation conditions, and the condensed phase is sent to wastewater treatment.

The CaL-based carbon capture system, illustrated in Fig. 2, consists of two circulating fluidized beds, a carbonator, and a calciner. In the carbonator, the CO₂ from the flue gas reacts with CaO to produce CaCO₃, and at the top, the solids and gases are separated using a cyclone. The solids containing the depleted sorbent are sent to the calciner, and a bag filter separates the decarbonized gases and entrained ashes. Then, the gases are sent to stack and the ashes to waste disposal. The solid sorbent is regenerated in the calciner using wood pellets as fuel and 95%_{vol} pure O₂ from an ASU as oxidant. A make-up of CaCO₃ is also introduced in the calciner and a purge stream is extracted from the solids entering the carbonator to maintain high reactivity in the fluidized beds and offset the deactivation of CaO after several cycles.

Part of the CO₂-rich stream at the top of the calciner is mixed with the O₂ from the ASU and recycled to the calciner to be used as fluidizing gas. The rest is cooled and separated from the ashes with a bag filter. The captured CO₂ is further purified and compressed in the compression and

purification unit (CPU), from which the off-gases are sent to the stack, the condensed phase to wastewater treatment, and the highly pure CO₂ to transportation.

No commercial applications of the CaL technology are in operation today. However, several high-TRL demonstrators have been developed to assess the system's energy and economic performances. The first plant of relevant size was developed during the CaOling project (CaOling, 2009) focused on the experimental pilot testing and scaling up of the process in the 1 MW range. This was built in the Hunosa 50 MW_e CFB coal power plant of "La Pereda" using a side stream of flue gases of the commercial plant. Then, additional development progress was carried out at the pilot plant built at the universities of Stuttgart (Dieter et al., 2014) and Darmstadt (Haaf et al., 2020).

The performance of the Bio-CHP plant's various configurations, with and without carbon capture, is reported in Table 1.

As can be observed, due to its technological design, the integration of the CaL system outperforms the amine-based scrubbing as it provides higher net electric efficiency (i.e., 22.52% vs. 19.69%), while resulting as well in lower net direct fossil emissions (i.e., -2748.2 kg CO₂/t_{wood} vs. -1079.9 kg CO₂/t_{wood}). In addition, one of the CaLby2030 tasks is to identify further strategies to increase the system's efficiency. For instance, reducing the calciner's temperature will enable a higher CO₂ capture rate due to the lower CO₂ equilibrium concentration related to the carbonation reaction. In addition, the injection of Ca(OH)₂ at the exit of the carbonator will increase the CO₂ capture efficiency due to sorbent's higher reactivity compared to CaO and the associated temperature reduction (Criado et al., 2024). Moreover, given that the vent gas of the purification unit has a non-negligible CO₂ concentration and flow rate, its recycling to the carbonator inlet would further boost the carbon capture rate.

Table 2 summarizes the technology scenarios for the decarbonization of the Bio-CHP plant considered in this work.

The block diagram for the investigated scenarios is presented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the MEA carbon capture system integrated within the Bio-CHP plant.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the CaL-based carbon capture system integrated within the Bio-CHP plant.

Table 1
Energy and CO₂-related performance of the Bio-CHP plant configurations.

	UoM	Bio-CHP	Bio-CHP + MEA	Bio-CHP + CaL
Fuel consumption	MW _{LHV}	135.3	135.3	224.7
Net electrical power output	MW _e	39.1	26.6	50.6
Net electric efficiency	%	28.90	19.69	22.52
Direct CO ₂ emissions at stack	kg CO ₂ /t wood	1342.0	132.8	364.4
CO ₂ avoided from flue gases	%	–	90.1	72.8
Net direct fossil emissions	kg CO ₂ /t wood	0.0	–1079.9	–2748.2

Table 2
Technology scenarios for the decarbonization of the Bio-CHP plant considered.

		Transportation method		
		Onshore pipeline (T1)	Onshore and offshore pipeline (T2)	Onshore pipeline, liquefaction and offshore ships (T3)
Capture technology	MEA	MEA-T1	MEA-T2	MEA-T3
	CaL	CaL-T1	CaL-T2	CaL-T3

2.2. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of the investigated cases

LCA calculates the environmental and human health impact of a certain process or product by focusing on a specific function and considering all life cycle stages. According to the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) via ISO 14040:2006 (i.e., principles and framework) (ISO 14040, 2006) and ISO 14044:2006 (i.e., requirements and guidelines) (ISO 14044, 2006), an LCA study consists of the following steps: Goal and scope definition, Life Cycle Inventory (LCI), Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA), and Interpretation. These steps are detailed in the next section.

2.2.1. Goal and scope definition

The current study aims to quantify and evaluate the environmental performance of a Bio-CHP unit equipped with a CaL-based post-combustion CO₂ capture system. The environmental efficiency of the calcium looping system will be evaluated against the state-of-the-art CO₂ capture technology, which is the reactive gas-liquid post-combustion

capture using MEA as a solvent. The study's target audience includes members working in energy-intensive industries such as waste-to-energy, iron and steel, and cement manufacturing. The present study is accessible to the general public (technical and non-technical), and the results generated provide important insights for the decarbonization of hard-to-abate sectors and decision-makers.

The functional unit (FU), which also serves as a reference for the input and output streams, assesses and quantifies the system's function performance. The reference flows of a given FU are the amounts of products or services required to properly complete the system function and generate that FU. For the current investigation, one ton of CO₂ captured was considered as the FU; thus, all environmental impact categories will be reported to one ton of captured CO₂.

System boundaries are defined as the limits that separate the unit processes under study from the environment or other units. The processes that will be either included or excluded from the LCA study are, in fact, determined by the system boundaries. In line with the ISO 14040:2006 standard, the system boundaries must take into consideration different unit activities and flows across all life cycle stages. There are four ways to define the limits of the system, depending on the goal of the investigation: i) cradle-to-grave, which covers stages from raw material extraction to the end-of-life treatment; ii) cradle-to-gate, which considers steps from raw material extraction to the production stage; iii) gate-to-gate, which solely covers the production phase; and iv) gate-to-grave which takes into account steps from the use to the end-of-life treatment. The current investigation is a cradle-to-gate LCA study as it addresses the whole manufacturing process from the supply chain of raw materials up to the final product. Therefore, as presented in Fig. 4, the following elements are included within the system boundaries: 1) upstream processes: electricity/fuel production, limestone extraction and transportation, MEA supply chain, oxygen generation from an ASU or as waste gas from water electrolysis, flue gases from Bio-CHP; 2) main process: CO₂ capture, purification and compression (CPU); and 3) downstream processes: disposal of waste materials (solid and liquid), degraded solvent treatment, CO₂ transportation and storage.

The geographical location and temporal system boundaries are among the most significant factors to consider while determining the analysis parameters. On the one hand, plant location/geographical boundary stems both from market conditions and product definition. On the other hand, the temporal limits are much more difficult to define as certain stages from the product's life cycle need to be estimated (i.e., disposal or reuse) since they occur in the future. The geographical and temporal boundaries of the system under investigation presume that the

Fig. 3. Block flow diagram for the investigated scenarios.

Fig. 4. System boundaries for the investigated scenarios.

plant is situated in Spain, in the Asturias region, and has a lifespan of 25 years.

2.2.2. Assumptions used in the LCA study

Several factors need to be considered when designing the LCA, particularly when factual data is either nonexistent or inaccessible, forcing the LCA practitioner to rely on estimations and assumptions. Nonetheless, these hypotheses may significantly impact on the study's findings. Therefore, it is recommended to carry out a number of sensitivity analyses to assess how these estimations and assumptions affect the system's performance. The following tables provide the assumptions considered for each boundary limit (i.e., upstream, primary, and downstream processes) of this study.

In particular, Tables 3 and 4 report the assumptions of the upstream stages (i.e., limestone extraction and transportation and MEA production and transportation) used in the CaL and MEA-based systems, respectively.

The data for the primary processes is derived from modeling and

simulation. Table 5 presents the primary assumptions of the reactive gas liquid (i.e., MEA as solvent) and CaL processes used for post-combustion CO₂ capture from a Bio-CHP plant.

Information regarding the downstream processes, such as the degradation of the solvent (i.e., MEA) and other contaminants emissions due to chemical reactions, is presented in Table 6.

The assumptions considered for the three cases of transportation (i.e., one onshore and two offshore) are presented in Table 7.

It is not always possible to account for all that was planned for the LCA, and it is frequently unreasonable to change the purpose and scope to accommodate the new data sets, therefore the limits in issue need to be addressed and justified (Curran, 2017). The following aspects represent the limits of the current LCA research as they are not included in the system boundaries: (i) construction and decommissioning of the facility; (ii) repair and maintenance activities; (iii) building transportation infrastructure (such as highways, railroads, and ships) as well as transportation vehicles; (iv) installation of unloading facilities; (v) human endeavors associated with labor tasks; (vi) high-magnitude,

Table 3
Assumptions considered for the limestone extraction and transportation.

Process	Assumptions		
Limestone extraction and transportation	Diesel consumption	0.36	l/t limestone extracted
	Groundwater	0.45	m ³ /t limestone extracted
	Surface water evaporation	8.12 × 10 ⁻³	m ³ /t limestone extracted
	Groundwater evaporation	2.12 × 10 ⁻²	m ³ /t limestone extracted
	Electricity ^a	2.17	kWh/t limestone extracted
	Transportation mode	Truck-trailer	
	Fuel used for transportation	Diesel	
	Distance	100	km

^a Electricity is considered to be provided both from the grid mix and from installed PV panels.

non-predictable, low-frequency occurrences (i.e., escapes, unintentional spills).

2.2.3. Life cycle inventory (LCI)

Life cycle inventory (LCI) follows the goal and scope definition stage and emerges as the process of building an inventory of reference flows for a specific process or product. It involves precise documentation of all input and output streams, including resources, raw materials, different types of energy, and pollutants in the air, water, and soil (ISO 14040, 2006).

The data sets included in the LCI stage can be classified either as primary or secondary data. While secondary data refers to information obtained from modelling, computations, estimations, or scientific literature, primary data provides information gathered through on-site measurements, interviews, and surveys. The current study made use of both types of data. When primary data (i.e., measurements and interviews) were unavailable, information from process modelling, simulation, and scientific literature was used. Whenever possible, measurements were taken on-site to support the modelling process. To address any questions or data discrepancies, data checks were carried

Table 4
Assumptions considered for the MEA production and transportation.

Process	Assumptions		
MEA production ^a	MEA is produced from ethylene oxide (EtO) and ammonia in excess. The reaction typically occurs in the liquid phase with 75% _{wt} ammonia in water. The pressure needs to be sufficiently high to avoid the vaporization of EtO and ammonia. A distillation process is used to separate the unreacted ammonia and water, which are recycled into the system. Any ammonia and water not consumed during the production process are considered as emissions to the air (Frauenkron et al., 2001).		
	In order to avoid the production of secondary and tertiary amines as by-products (i.e., diethanolamine-DEA and triethanolamine-TEA), an excess ratio of NH ₃ :EtO of 10 : 1 is assumed to be sufficient to practically produce only MEA.		
	Electricity used for multi-stage distillation process (IEAGHG, 2006)	5	MJ/kg MEA produced
	Emissions to air obtained from the production of MEA (Pehnt and Henkel, 2009):		
	CO ₂	3.13	kg/kg MEA produced
	CO	2.02	g/kg MEA produced
	Ethylene	0.17	g/kg MEA produced
	Ethylene oxide	1.64	g/kg MEA produced
	Ammonia	23	g/kg MEA produced
	Methane	6.71	g/kg MEA produced
	NM VOC	2.02	g/kg MEA produced
	NO _x	7.32	g/kg MEA produced
	PM 2.5 μm	7.27	g/kg MEA produced
	PM 10 μm	4.63 × 10 ⁻¹	g/kg MEA produced
PM > 10 μm	7.85 × 10 ⁻¹	g/kg MEA produced	
SO ₂	8.66	g/kg MEA produced	
MEA transportation ^a	Transportation mode	Rail using cargo train	
	Fuel used for transportation	Diesel/Electricity	
	Distance (Germany to Spain)	2000 km	

^a LCA for Experts pre-defined processes were used for the production of EtO (obtained by oxidation of ethylene with air) and ammonia (produced by the Haber-Bosch process). The MEA supplier was considered the BASF in Germany.

out iteratively. Regarding the technical coverage and resource supply chain, the overall data quality is thought to be excellent and representative of the systems under investigation. The most relevant data sets for the CaL-based process, limestone extraction and transportation, and CO₂ transportation both onshore and offshore are presented in the Supplementary Materials file.

2.2.4. Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA)

The goal of the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) step is to establish a link between the elementary flows of the system and any potential impacts on the environment. Given that the LCI step includes various input and output flows (such as resources, emissions, and others), the LCIA phase translates the reference flows into environmental impact categories.

Regarding well-known and straightforward effect indicators, all inventory results are pre-categorized to pre-selected impact categories already included in several LCA software applications (e.g., SimaPRO and LCA for Experts) and for which characterization factors have already been determined. LCA for Experts version 10.8 by Sphera® was

Table 5
Assumptions considered for the main processes (De Lena et al., 2024).

Process	Assumptions		
CaL and MEA capture systems	Operating hours	8000	h/year
	Location	Downstream of the Bio-CHP power plant, after the flue gas treatment plant.	
CaL capture system	Net electricity produced	11.5	MWe
	Limestone make-up	7.22	t/h
	Oxygen used for combustion in the calciner comes from a cryogenic ASU, with an energy consumption of 240–250 kWh/t O ₂ produced.		
MEA capture system	Wood pellets are considered to be used as fuel in the calciner.		
	Landfill disposal was assumed for the solid waste.		
	MEA make-up (Morken et al., 2017).	1.6	kg MEA/t CO ₂ captured
	The steam required for solvent regeneration is supplied by a steam turbine bleeding directly from the power plant. This results in a gross electric power loss in the steam turbine of about 7.1 MWe.		

Table 6
Assumptions considered for the MEA degradation and contaminants formation.

Process	Assumptions												
MEA degradation	For the degradation of MEA, only the oxidation reaction was considered. Based on experimental studies, the following degradation reaction was applied (Léonard et al., 2015): $MEA + 0.33O_2 \rightarrow 0.6NH_3 + 0.1HEI + 0.1HEPO + 0.1HCOOH + 0.8CO_2 + 1.5H_2O$ Only ammonia, formic acid, carbon dioxide, and water were considered as degradation products of MEA. The other substances (i.e., HEI = N-(2-hydroxyethyl) imidazole and HEPO = 4-(2-hydroxyethyl) piperazine-2-one) were not found in the LCA for Experts database.												
Emissions of pollutants due to chemical solvent reactions	The decarbonized flue gas to stack resulting at the exit of the absorber contains a series of contaminants derived from the chemical reaction with the solvent (i.e., MEA). According to the literature, the primary contaminants (scaled for the current process) are (Morken et al., 2014): <table border="1" style="margin-left: 20px;"> <tr> <td>MEA</td> <td>3.626</td> <td>g/h</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Ammonia</td> <td>819</td> <td>g/h</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Formaldehyde</td> <td>0.499</td> <td>g/h</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Acetaldehyde</td> <td>3.675</td> <td>g/h</td> </tr> </table>	MEA	3.626	g/h	Ammonia	819	g/h	Formaldehyde	0.499	g/h	Acetaldehyde	3.675	g/h
MEA	3.626	g/h											
Ammonia	819	g/h											
Formaldehyde	0.499	g/h											
Acetaldehyde	3.675	g/h											

Table 7
Assumptions considered for the CO₂ transportation.

Process	Assumptions		
CO ₂ transportation onshore (T1)	Onshore transportation via pipeline	270	km
	Electricity for compression/reconditioning	0.1	kWh/kg CO ₂ transported
	CO ₂ losses (pipelines, compressors and injection)	0.01	%
CO ₂ transportation offshore (T2)	Onshore section via pipeline	30	km
	Offshore section via pipeline	1000	km
	Electricity for compression/reconditioning	0.1	kWh/kg CO ₂ transported
CO ₂ transportation offshore (T3)	CO ₂ losses (pipelines, compressors and injection)	0.01	%
	Onshore section via pipeline	30	km
	Offshore shipping	1000	km
	Liquefaction energy	0.246	kWh/kg CO ₂ transported
	Boil-off rate ^a	1000	kg CO ₂ /h
	Ships heavy fuel consumption	3435	t/year
	CO ₂ losses (pipelines, compressors and injection)	0.01	%

^a The CO₂ emission results from heating the tank during transportation, due to engine operation and other activities on the ship. Releasing the gas formed is necessary to prevent over-pressurizing the tank.

chosen as the LCA software application for the current study.

The Life Cycle Initiative established a framework linking inventory data to environmental impacts. Initially, data with similar effects are

grouped into midpoint categories. Each input and output flows are assigned to a characterization factor indicating its contribution to these categories. Midpoint categories are then connected to damage categories addressing negative impacts on areas like human health, ecological damage, and resource depletion, known as endpoint indicators. Impact categories can thus be classified as damage-oriented strategies (endpoint method) or problem-oriented strategies (midpoint method) (Pillain et al., 2017). In the cause-and-effect chain, endpoint categories are positioned at the end and have greater uncertainty about the parameters but are easier to interpret. In contrast, midpoint impact indicators are positioned early in the chain and provide more accurate findings with less uncertainty, yet their interpretation is more complex (Motahari et al., 2024). Considering the goal of the present study, the ReCiPe 2016 impact assessment method was used to perform the current environmental investigation. The environmental impact categories provided by

Table 8
Overview and description of the environmental impact indicators based on the ReCiPe 2016 impact assessment method (Huijbregts et al., 2017).

Impact indicator	Characterization	Main contributors
Global Warming Potential (GWP)	Anthropogenic emissions leading to an increase in the surface temperature. Unit: kg of CO ₂ equivalents to air.	CO ₂ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O, NO ₂ , CFCs, HCFCs, HFCs.
Freshwater Eutrophication Potential (FEP)	Excessive quantities of nutrients detected in the internal water ecosystem. Unit: kg of P equivalents to freshwater.	Nitrogen and phosphorus chemicals.
Stratospheric Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP)	Anthropogenic emissions that are causing the stratospheric ozone layer to thin. Unit: kg of CFC-11 equivalents to air.	CFCs, HCFCs, halons.
Fossil Depletion Potential (FDP)	Excess energy used for the extraction of one MJ, kg or m ³ of fossil fuel. Unit: kg of oil equivalents (with a lower heating value of 42 MJ).	Extraction of fossil resources.
Mineral Depletion Potential (MDP)	Ore grade decrease. Unit: kg of Cu equivalents.	Extraction of mineral resources.
Photochemical Oxidant Formation Potential (POFP _{ecosystem})	Increase in ozone concentration at the troposphere level. Unit: kg of NO _x equivalents to air.	Particulate matter, NMVOCs, NO _x .
Photochemical Oxidant Formation Potential human health (POFP _{human-health})	Tropospheric ozone population intake increases. Unit: kg of NO _x equivalents to air.	Particulate matter, NMVOCs, NO _x .
Human Toxicity Potential cancer (HTP _{cancer})	Risk increases of cancer disease incidence. Unit: kg of 1,4 DCB equivalents to air.	Chemical substances toxic to human health
Human Toxicity Potential non-cancer (HTP _{non-cancer})	Risk increases of non-cancer disease incidence. Unit: kg of 1,4 DCB equivalents to air.	Chemical substances toxic to human health
Freshwater Ecotoxicity Potential (FETP)	Relates to the possible harm of toxic compounds to the aquatic environment. Unit: kg of 1,4 DCB equivalents to freshwater.	Toxic chemicals with a reported lethal concentration to rodents and fish (i.e., Pb, Hg, Cd, halogenated organic compounds, pesticides, or sewage sludge).
Terrestrial Ecotoxicity Potential (TETP)	Accounts for the potential impact of toxic substances on terrestrial ecosystems. Unit: kg of 1,4 DCB equivalents to industrial soil.	

the ReCiPe 2016 assessment method are further detailed in Table 8 (Huijbregts et al., 2017).

3. Results and discussions

The main goal of the interpretation stage is to provide recommendations and conclusions considering the research limitations, the issues identified in the LCI and LCIA results, and the goals and scope of the investigation (ISO 14040, 2006). The intended audience of the study should be able to comprehend easily the evaluation results when presented. Table 9 presents the LCA results for the evaluated scenarios for the Bio-CHP integrated with either MEA-or CaL-based technology, taking into account the assumptions and limitations of the study previously presented. As can be noticed from Table 9, the environmental analysis considered three cases based on different CO₂ transportation scenarios (i.e., T1: onshore transportation by pipelines, T2: onshore and offshore transport by pipelines, and T3: onshore transport by pipelines and offshore by ships). As mentioned in Section 2.2.1, all environmental impact categories refer to one ton of CO₂ captured to ensure a fair comparison across the various scenarios. When comparing the three options, the first case scenario, T1, which solely considers the onshore pipeline transportation of CO₂, yields the best results. On the opposite, the third investigated option, T3, exhibits the largest impact due to the offshore CO₂ transportation by ships. Of all environmental effect categories, the FDP impact score in T3 increased the highest, nearly thirteen times, when compared to T1, primarily due to the use of heavy fuel by ships. In addition, the GWP increased by about three times between T1 and T3. When examining MEA-T1 against CaL-T1, one can notice that the CaL system exhibits the best results in ten out of eleven impact categories studied (i.e., GWP, FDP, FETP, FEP, HTP_{cancer}, HTP_{non-cancer}, POFP_{ecosystem}, POFP_{human-health}, ODP, and TETP) with values between 1.1 and 2.9 times lower, only the MDP impact score is about 4.5 times larger for the CaL case. In addition, the overall difference in CO₂ capture efficiency between the reactive MEA and CaL was assessed. Comparing the CaL technology to the amine-based system, CO₂ emissions were reduced by approximately 25%, which is consistent with the results presented by Haran et al. (2023).

The next section highlights the main sub-systems that contribute most to each environmental indicator in the best scenario, i.e., CaL-T1.

3.1. Global warming potential (GWP) indicator

Fig. 5 illustrates a detailed distribution of the GWP indicator, thus presenting the sub-processes that contribute the most (i.e., limestone supply chain, CaL-based CO₂ capture, and CO₂ transportation). The CaL system has the largest influence, contributing 84.93% of the total 180.84 kg CO₂ eq./t CO₂ captured. CO₂ transportation ranks second with a share of 14.18% or 25.64 kg CO₂ eq./t CO₂ captured. With a share of 0.89%, the supply chain for limestone is the smallest contribution. Upon further examination of the CaL system, the primary sources of the 160.81 kg CO₂ eq./t CO₂ captured are the vent gases from the CO₂ compression and

purification unit (e.g., roughly 61% share) along with the flue gases to stack (e.g., 39% share). As observed, negative emissions are registered due to electricity generation throughout the CaL process (e.g., -8.21 kg CO₂ eq./t CO₂ captured). It has been considered that the electricity may be supplied to the grid, removing the need for additional fuel (e.g., natural gas, coal, biomass) and thus cutting the CO₂ emissions. Solid waste disposal accounts for approximately 0.98 kg CO₂ eq./t CO₂ captured of the total GWP score. As previously stated, the onshore CO₂ transportation contributes by 25.64 kg CO₂ eq./t CO₂ captured; however, CO₂ losses account for less than 0.4% of the total value, the remaining of 99.6% being due to the conditioning for CO₂ injection.

3.2. Fossil depletion potential (FDP) indicator

The FDP indicator is related to the extraction of fossil resources. The contribution of each sub-process to the overall FDP value in the CaL-T1 (e.g., 12.64 kg oil eq./t CO₂ captured) is illustrated in Fig. 6. Electricity generation and supply for the CO₂ conditioning for injection ranks as the main contributor with 14.10 kg oil eq./t CO₂ captured of the total impact. Assuming solely the onshore transportation of CO₂ in CaL-T1, the power used for conditioning is assumed to be supplied from Spain's grid mix. According to the LCA Sphera database (LCA Database, 2024), the following sources account for the majority of Spain's power production: natural gas (26.50%), nuclear (22.15%), wind (21.44%), hydro (12.93%), photovoltaics (5.96%), fuel oil (4.07%), hard coal (2.10%), biomass (1.73%) and waste (0.67%). Since the CaL system generates electricity through the use of biomass as fuel, it adds negative emissions to the overall FDP indicator (e.g., -1.80 kg oil eq./t CO₂ captured). Solid waste disposal and limestone supply chain contribute by 0.30 kg oil eq./t CO₂ captured and 0.35 kg oil eq./t CO₂ captured, respectively. Of the total limestone supply chain contribution, 84% is due to transportation and 16% to extraction.

3.3. Freshwater ecotoxicity potential (FETP) indicator

The potential impacts of toxic substances on aquatic ecosystems are linked to the FETP environmental impact indicator. The overall FETP value in CaL-T1 is 1.31×10^{-1} kg 1,4-DB eq./t CO₂ captured. As Fig. 7 shows, the CaL system exhibits the largest contribution, accounting for 98.14% of the total share, mainly due to the wastewater treatment sub-process. Following the same reasoning, the net energy generated by the CaL system provides a negative contribution, as it eliminates the need to produce energy from other sources that would release harmful environmental emissions. In addition, 1.70% share of the overall value of FETP is related to the electricity required for CO₂ conditioning during the transportation phase. In contrast, the limestone supply chain has a far lesser impact—only 0.15%.

3.4. Freshwater eutrophication potential (FEP) indicator

The freshwater ecosystem's nutrient content, particularly in terms of

Table 9

LCA results for the Bio-CHP scenarios for MEA and CaL-based systems.

KPI	Units	MEA-T1	CaL-T1	MEA-T2	CaL-T2	MEA-T3	CaL-T3
GWP	kg CO ₂ eq./t CO ₂ captured	248.43	180.84	274.06	206.47	561.08	493.49
FDP	kg oil eq./t CO ₂ captured	16.63	12.64	30.72	26.74	166.82	162.84
FETP	kg 1,4-DB eq./t CO ₂ captured	1.58×10^{-1}	1.31×10^{-1}	1.61×10^{-1}	1.33×10^{-1}	2.32×10^{-1}	2.05×10^{-1}
FEP	kg P eq./t CO ₂ captured	4.22×10^{-3}	1.44×10^{-3}	4.27×10^{-3}	1.48×10^{-3}	4.41×10^{-3}	1.63×10^{-3}
HTP _{cancer}	kg 1,4-DB eq./t CO ₂ captured	6.49×10^{-1}	4.64×10^{-1}	6.77×10^{-1}	4.91×10^{-1}	7.99×10^{-1}	6.13×10^{-1}
HTP _{non cancer}	kg 1,4-DB eq./t CO ₂ captured	62.68	55.20	62.91	55.43	91.22	83.74
MDP	kg Cu eq./t CO ₂ captured	3.35×10^{-2}	0.15	5.94×10^{-2}	0.18	0.11	0.23
POFP _{ecosystem}	kg NOx eq./t CO ₂ captured	4.48×10^{-2}	-0.26	6.87×10^{-2}	-0.24	0.23	-0.08
POFP _{human health}	kg NOx eq./t CO ₂ captured	4.35×10^{-2}	-0.25	6.70×10^{-2}	-0.23	0.21	-0.09
ODP	kg CFC-11 eq./t CO ₂ captured	1.48×10^{-5}	-5.41×10^{-5}	2.49×10^{-5}	-4.40×10^{-5}	4.54×10^{-5}	-2.36×10^{-5}
TETP	kg 1,4-DB eq./t CO ₂ captured	14.07	-8.89	16.51	-6.47	52.34	29.37

Fig. 5. GWP indicator distribution for CaL-T1.

Fig. 6. FDP indicator distribution for CaL-T1.

Fig. 7. FETP indicator distribution for CaL-T1.

nitrogen and phosphorus, is indicated by the FEP indicator, which is expressed in kg of phosphorous equivalents. As reported in Tables 9 and in the CaL-T1, the total score in terms of FEP is.

$1.44 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg P eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}$. The overall distribution of the FEP impact category is illustrated in Fig. 8. The wastewater treatment process ranks first with the largest contribution, $3.79 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg P eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}$. Conversely, a negative contribution of $2.40 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg P eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}$ is due to the electricity production through the CaL system. With contributions of 3.09% and 0.33%, respectively, the CO₂ transportation and limestone supply chain exhibit a considerably lesser impact.

3.5. Human toxicity potential cancer (HTP_{cancer}) indicator

Fig. 9 displays the primary contributing sub-systems to the total HTP_{cancer} indicator, which measures the potential harm of a substance with regard to cancer. As reported in Table 9, the total impact value of the HTP_{cancer} indicator for CaL-T1 is $4.64 \times 10^{-1} \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$. The CaL system accounts for 94.01% of the total score, while CO₂ transportation ranks second with a share of 5.93%. At just 0.06%, the limestone supply chain contributes the least to the overall value of HTP_{cancer}. From the CaL system, the HTP_{cancer} category is most influenced by the wastewater treatment process, contributing by $0.56 \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$. The CaL system adds a negative contribution (e.g., $-0.12 \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$) to the overall HTP_{cancer} indicator as it generates electricity. The CO₂ transportation contributes by $2.75 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$ to the total score due to the conditioning process. Solid waste disposal, limestone transportation, and limestone extraction each present a significantly lower influence (e.g., $2.65 \times 10^{-4} \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$, $2.50 \times 10^{-4} \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$, and $0.47 \times 10^{-4} \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$).

3.6. Human toxicity potential non-cancer (HTP_{non-cancer}) indicator

Toxic substances are examined for their effects on human health without causing cancer by using the HTP_{non-cancer}. For CaL-T1, the overall HTP_{non-cancer} value is $55.20 \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$. Fig. 10 displays the HTP_{non-cancer} distribution to highlight the sub-systems with the highest influence. As can be observed, the CaL CO₂ capture system ranks first with a share of 99.39% of the overall impact. The contributions of limestone supply chain and CO₂ transportation are 0.42% and 0.19%, respectively. Looking at the CaL sub-system, the wastewater treatment process is the first contributor (e.g., $56.71 \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$). Similarly, to the previously discussed impact categories, the

negative contribution of $-1.90 \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$ is due to the electricity generated. Solid waste disposal adds $5.58 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$ to the total value of HTP_{non-cancer} indicator.

3.7. Mineral depletion potential (MDP) indicator

The MDP indicator illustrates how the process contributes to reducing ore grades. Fig. 11 displays the contributions of the sub-processes to the MDP indicator. For CaL-T1, the overall value of the MDP environmental impact indicator is $0.15 \text{ kg}_{\text{Cu eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$, as shown in.

Table 9. The CaL system accounts for approximately 82% of the total MDP impact score, while CO₂ transportation ranks second with a contribution of nearly 17%. At 1.32% share, the supply chain for limestone makes the least contribution. By examining the CaL process more closely, it can be noted that the most significant contribution (e.g., $0.40 \text{ kg}_{\text{Cu eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$) is determined by the solid waste disposal. With a value of $-0.27 \text{ kg}_{\text{Cu eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$, the power generated by the CaL process makes a negative contribution to the overall MDP score. The negative number shows that mineral resources are conserved and do not need to be used to generate the amount of power produced by the CaL system (e.g., $193.38 \text{ kWh/t CO}_2 \text{ captured}$). The CO₂ transport process contributes by $2.58 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg}_{\text{Cu eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$ due to electricity demand, while limestone extraction and transportation show a significantly lower contribution (e.g., 3.00×10^{-4} and $1.72 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg}_{\text{Cu eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$, respectively).

3.8. Photochemical ozone formation potential ecosystem (POFP_{ecosystem}) indicator

The total impact for the POFP_{ecosystem} category in CaL-T1 is $-0.26 \text{ kg}_{\text{NOx eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$, as reported in Table 9. The POFP_{ecosystem} indicator refers to the increase in the concentration of chemical compounds such as ozone at the troposphere level. The POFP_{ecosystem} distribution and the influence of various sub-processes are depicted in Fig. 12. The CO₂ transportation process accounts for $2.40 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg}_{\text{NOx eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$, whereas the limestone transportation has a contribution of $6.47 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg}_{\text{NOx eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$. The extraction of limestone impacts the overall score by $7.28 \times 10^{-5} \text{ kg}_{\text{NOx eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$. Nevertheless, the largest contribution comes from the energy generated from biomass in the CaL process, $-0.29 \text{ kg}_{\text{NOx eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$.

Fig. 8. FEP indicator distribution for CaL-T1.

Fig. 9. HTP_{cancer} indicator distribution for CaL-T1.

Fig. 10. HTP_{non-cancer} indicator distribution for CaL-T1.

Fig. 11. MDP indicator distribution for CaL-T1.

Fig. 12. POFP_{ecosystem} indicator distribution for CaL-T1.

3.9. Photochemical ozone formation potential human-health (POFP_{human-health}) indicator

The increase in species concentration that influences the impact of tropospheric ozone pollution on human health is referred to as the POFP_{human-health} impact indicator. Fig. 13 shows the contribution of each sub-process to the overall value of POFP_{human-health}. The total impact score for the CaL Case 1 is $-0.25 \text{ kg NO}_x \text{ eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}$. With $-0.29 \text{ kg NO}_x \text{ eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}$, the electricity generated during the CaL CO₂ capture process makes up the highest contribution. This sub-process is followed by CO₂ transportation, adding $2.36 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg NO}_x \text{ eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}$. Significantly lesser contributions may be seen when looking at limestone extraction and transportation, as well as solid waste disposal.

3.10. Stratospheric ozone depletion potential (ODP) indicator

The ODP impact category measures the anthropogenic emissions that contribute to the reduction of the stratospheric ozone layer. As reported in Table 9, the total score of the ODP indicator in CaL-T1 is $-5.41 \times 10^{-5} \text{ kg CFC-11 eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}$. Fig. 14 presents the contribution of the various sub-systems to the total value of the ODP indicator. Similarly, to the previous impact categories, the net electricity produced by the CaL

process exhibits the largest influence, contributing by $-7.97 \times 10^{-5} \text{ kg CFC-11 eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}$. The limestone extraction and the CO₂ conditioning rank among the main contributors with $1.45 \times 10^{-5} \text{ kg CFC-11 eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}$ and $1.02 \times 10^{-5} \text{ kg CFC-11 eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}$, respectively. Limestone transportation and solid waste disposal have considerably less influence than other sub-processes.

3.11. Terrestrial ecotoxicity potential (TETP) indicator

The TETP indicator relates to the effect of toxic substances on terrestrial ecosystems and sediment environments. In the CaL-T1, the TETP impact category has a total score of $-8.89 \text{ kg 1,4-DB eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}$. Fig. 15 illustrates the sub-processes with the largest influence over the TETP indicator. The electricity produced and used in the CO₂ transportation brings a contribution of $2.43 \text{ kg 1,4-DB eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}$, while the solid waste disposal adds $0.10 \text{ kg 1,4-DB eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}$. Limestone extraction and transportation have much lower contributions. Similar to the preceding impact categories, the TETP indicator's total impact decreased by $-11.51 \text{ kg 1,4-DB eq./t CO}_2 \text{ captured}$ due to the electricity generated by the CaL process.

Fig. 13. POFP_{human-health} indicator distribution for CaL-T1.

Fig. 14. ODP indicator distribution for CaL-T1.

Fig. 15. TETP indicator distribution for CaL-T1.

4. Conclusions

The current study aims to assess the environmental performance of the CaL-based CO₂ capture system integrated within a Bio-CHP facility located in the Asturias region, Spain. The environmental performance of the CaL-based system is compared against the conventional reactive gas-liquid CO₂ capture using MEA as solvent.

The environmental analysis focuses on three potential CO₂ transportation scenarios, one onshore and the others offshore, and evaluates both MEA and CaL-based CO₂ capture systems. The following cases have been investigated: MEA-T1, CaL-T1 (MEA and CaL with onshore transportation via pipelines); MEA-T2, CaL-T2 (MEA and CaL with offshore transportation via pipelines); and MEA-T3, CaL-T3 (MEA and CaL with onshore CO₂ transportation via pipelines, CO₂ liquefaction and offshore transportation with ships). The key environmental findings are outlined below.

1. When examining the CO₂ transportation alternatives, the first scenario (T1) produces the best outcomes since it only considers CO₂ transportation via onshore pipeline. On the contrary, the third

scenario (i.e., offshore CO₂ shipping) has the highest impact given the additional electricity required for CO₂ liquefaction.

2. Out of all the environmental impact categories, the FDP indicator in T3 increased the most, roughly thirteen times, in comparison to T1, and about six times when compared to T2. This is mostly because of the heavy fuel used by the ships.
3. The CaL system outperforms the MEA-based CO₂ capture in ten of the eleven impact categories that were examined (i.e., GWP, FDP, FETP, FEP, HTP_{cancer}, HTP_{non-cancer}, POFP_{ecosystem}, POFP_{human-health}, ODP, and TETP).
4. In the CaL-based CO₂ capture approach, the carbon capture process ranks first with approximately 85% share of the total GWP score, followed by CO₂ transportation with a contribution of 14.18%, representing around 25.64 kg CO₂ eq./t CO₂ captured.
5. The use of renewable energy sources could help lower the impact score of the FDP category, as the generation and supply of electricity for the CO₂ conditioning process is the primary contributor.

To decarbonize the heat and power sector and facilitate the deployment of cleaner technologies, the results of the present research

offer important insights into the advantages of integrating post-combustion carbon capture with proper CO₂ transportation strategies. A key conclusion is that CaL technology demonstrates superior performance compared to the established amine scrubbing system, both in terms of net electric power output and direct fossil CO₂ emissions (i.e., 50.6 MW_e vs. 26.6 MW_e and -1079.9 kg CO₂/t_{wood} vs. -2748.2 kg CO₂/t_{wood}), while also exhibiting a lower environmental impact.

Finding and implementing methods that are consistent with the technology at hand is an ongoing challenge in the transition of carbon-intensive and high-emission industries towards net-zero emissions. To support informed decision-making and ensure a comprehensive evaluation from a national perspective, it is essential to extend the analysis to a cradle-to-grave system. Furthermore, additional efforts should focus on investigating geographical and temporal constraints, as the location plays a crucial role in influencing environmental performance.

Technical improvements can also enhance cleaner and more sustainable production pathways. Reducing the calciner temperature can lead to a higher CO₂ capture rate, as it lowers the CO₂ equilibrium concentration in the carbonation reaction. The integration of solid heat recovery, through a solid-solid heat exchanger that recovers heat from the sorbent at the reactor exit, further optimizes energy efficiency. Cooling CaO at 920 °C to preheat partially carbonated sorbent at 650 °C contributes to a more energy-efficient process. Additionally, injecting Ca(OH)₂ at the carbonator exit increases CO₂ capture efficiency, owing to the higher reactivity of this sorbent compared to CaO, along with the associated temperature reduction. These considerations are vital for fostering cleaner and more sustainable production practices.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Letitia Petrescu: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Stefan**

Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Nomenclature

ASU	Air Separation Unit
CaL	Calcium Looping
CCUS	Carbon Capture Utilization and Storage
CFB	Circulating Fluidized Bed
CFCs	Chlorofluorocarbons
CHP	Combined heat and power
CPU	Compression and Purification Unit
DEA	Diethanolamine
DCB	Dichlorobenzene
EtO	Ethylene Oxide
FDP	Fossil fuel Depletion Potential
FEP	Freshwater Eutrophication Potential
FETP	Freshwater Ecotoxicity Potential
FU	Functional unit
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GWP	Global Warming Potential
HCFC	Hydrochlorofluorocarbons
HTP _{cancer}	Human Toxicity Potential cancer
HTP _{non-cancer}	Human Toxicity Potential non-cancer
IEA	International Energy Agency
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISO	International Standardization Organization
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
MDP	Mineral Depletion Potential
MEA	Mono-Ethanol-Amine
NMVOCS	Non-methane volatile organic compounds
NZE	Net-Zero Emission

(continued on next page)

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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(continued)

ODP	Stratospheric Ozone Depletion Potential
POFP _{ecosystem}	Photochemical Oxidant Formation Potential ecosystem
POFP _{human-health}	Photochemical Oxidant Formation Potential human-health
TETP	Terrestrial Ecotoxicity Potential
TEA	Triethanolamine

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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